

Complex Revascularization in a Patient with Recurrent Deep Vein Thrombosis and Chronic Iliac Stent Occlusions Utilizing the Kodiak Co-Axial Reinforced Introducer System: A Case Report

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Abstract

This case report presents the clinical complexities and synergistic interventional strategies in the management of a 62-year-old male with a significant medical history complicated by recurrent deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE). Despite a history of extensive therapeutic interventions including anticoagulation failures, ilio caval reconstruction, and peripheral thrombectomy, the patient exhibited recurrent symptoms related to venous stent occlusions. The intricacies of his case are accentuated by a multi-faceted medical background including hypertension, heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), hyperlipidemia, hypothyroidism, anxiety, depression, peptic ulcer disease, and a history of diverticulitis requiring sigmoidectomy and colostomy.

Following an episode of lower gastrointestinal bleeding which necessitated the temporary cessation of anticoagulation therapy, the patient developed progressive right lower extremity pain, nonspecific abdominal pain, constipation, and occasional small volume lower GI bleeding. Diagnostic evaluation with CT imaging indicated possible occlusion of his previously placed right iliac stents and distension of ventral wall varices. These findings prompted a coordinated interventional response.

The interventional procedure utilized a range of novel and traditional devices and techniques. Initial vascular access was achieved via the right internal jugular and bilateral groin approaches. The use of the Contego Excipio XL device as an IVC embolic protection showcased a novel approach to managing potential embolic risks during complex revascularizations. Despite challenges in navigating the occluded stents, advanced techniques including the use of Kodiak Reinforced Co-Axial Introducer System and Mustang balloons facilitated the creation of a new luminal pathway. This was followed by extensive thrombectomy using the Penumbra FLASH 16 and Excipio XL systems, culminating in successful revascularization as confirmed by repeat venography and intravascular ultrasound (IVUS). IVUS findings revealed synechia and stenosis, which were managed with targeted venoplasty and the strategic placement of an Abre 12mm stent extension, resulting in restored brisk venous flow.

This case demonstrates the intricate decision-making and adjunctive techniques required in managing severe, recurrent vascular conditions in patients with complex medical histories.

It also highlights the importance of adaptive strategies in interventional radiology, including the trial of new devices and techniques in the face of challenging anatomical and clinical scenarios. The successful resolution of symptoms following these interventions demonstrates the potential for innovative approaches to significantly impact patient outcomes in complex vascular cases.

Keywords: Kodiak, Occlusion, Re-Cannulation, Venous Stenting, Venous Thromboembolism

1. Introduction

Chronic venous insufficiency (CVI) is a common complication among patients with a history of deep vein thrombosis (DVT), particularly when it involves the ilio caval segment.(McArdle and Hernandez-Vila 2017) The condition is characterized by persistent inadequate venous return over a prolonged period, often exacerbated by occlusive episodes within the venous stents previously placed to manage venous thromboembolism. This can lead to significant morbidity, including leg pain, swelling, and even ulcerations, presenting substantial challenges in clinical management.(Schwein et al. 2018) The patient described in this case report represents a particularly complex scenario due to the recurrence of DVT despite standard therapeutic interventions and the failure of anticoagulation strategies, highlighting the difficulties in achieving long-term patency and symptom control.

In cases where standard anticoagulation fails, patients are at increased risk of both recurrent thrombosis and post-thrombotic syndrome, which significantly impacts their quality of life. These patients often require more than pharmacological therapy alone; interventional strategies become crucial. The therapeutic approach for managing CVI due to ilio caval occlusion needs to be multifaceted, involving careful consideration of both the anatomical challenges and the patient's broader medical history. This includes evaluating the risks and benefits of repeated interventions, the choice of stenting and thrombectomy techniques, and the management of anticoagulation therapy post-procedure.

The current case emphasizes the importance of a tailored approach that incorporates novel interventional technologies and techniques. In such complex scenarios, standard treatment protocols may not suffice, and innovative strategies become necessitated. The use of multi-modality imaging for precise diagnosis and guidance during interventions, selection of specific devices suited to the patient's anatomical challenges, and a proactive approach to managing potential complications are all critical elements in the treatment regimen. (Müller, Nestor L. 2001.) These measures are aimed at not only addressing the immediate complications associated with ilio caval occlusion but also at preventing long-term sequelae such as chronic pain and limb swelling.

Thus, the management of recurrent, complex DVT and CVI requires an interdisciplinary approach that goes beyond conventional medical treatment.(Midulla et al. 2020) It necessitates collaboration across specialties including interventional radiology, vascular surgery,

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and hematology to optimize patient outcomes. This case serves as an instructive example of the complexities involved in such cases and the potential of interventional radiology to adapt to and effectively manage challenging vascular conditions.

Case Presentation:

The patient, a 62-year-old male, has a complex medical history that includes several chronic conditions: hypertension, heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), hyperlipidemia, hypothyroidism, anxiety, depression, peptic ulcer disease (PUD), and a history of diverticulitis leading to sigmoidectomy and colostomy. His vascular history is particularly significant, with recurrent episodes of deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE), which have previously necessitated advanced interventional treatments and long-term anticoagulation therapy.

This case began with the patient's presentation at the clinic, where he reported new-onset right lower extremity pain and nonspecific abdominal pain. These symptoms emerged during a period when his routine anticoagulation therapy was temporarily discontinued due to an episode of lower gastrointestinal bleeding, necessitating hospitalization. The cessation of anticoagulation, although necessary, predisposed him to thrombotic complications given his history of venous thromboembolism.

Upon re-evaluation, diagnostic imaging, specifically a computed tomography (CT) scan, was performed to diagnose the cause of his symptoms. The imaging demonstrated complete occlusion of the right iliac stents previously placed for managing chronic venous insufficiency and recurrent DVT. The occlusion was accompanied by increased distension of ventral wall varices, indicative of aggravated chronic venous pressure and stasis, contributing to his symptomatology.

The clinical decision to proceed with an interventional approach was based on the imaging results and the patient's deteriorating clinical symptomology. The objective was to address the stent occlusion, restore venous patency, and alleviate the symptoms while managing the risks associated with re-intervention, particularly in a patient with multiple comorbidities and a history of complicated postoperative courses. This case underscores the intricate balance required in managing chronic conditions alongside acute interventions, particularly in patients with extensive medical histories and complex, interrelated health issues.

2. Interventional Procedure:

Access and Embolic Protection: The procedure commenced with securing vascular access through the right internal jugular (RIJ) and bilateral groin. This approach provided optimal angles for interventional approach and device deployment. The Contego Excipio XL device was deployed within the inferior vena cava (IVC) to serve as a temporary embolic protection system. The utilization of the Excipio XL or similar filtration/embolic protective devices should be considered in such procedures to capture and remove any dislodged material during the intervention, thus minimizing the risk of pulmonary embolism or other embolic events.

Crossing the Occlusion: Initial attempts to navigate through the occluded segments of the right iliac stents with a Navicross catheter and Glidewire proved unsuccessful. These

tools slipped along the edge of the stent rather than penetrating the occlusion. The interventional team then opted to employ the Kodiak Introducer system from Argon Medical Devices, which is designed to offer a combination of flexibility and rigidity, making it ideal for negotiating tough, fibrotic stenoses in vascular channels.

The kit includes a large-bore sheath and a Y-shaped adapter that enables the simultaneous introduction of multiple components through a single access site. This feature significantly simplifies complex procedures by allowing various instruments to be used concurrently while maintaining a stable and reliable access point.

The Kodiak system is particularly suited for use in situations where the anatomy presents challenges, such as dense scar tissue or occlusions within vascular stents. Its construction features include hemostasis valves within the Y-connector and sheaths which nest co-axial and are all reinforced, which help prevent bleed-back and minimize blood loss. The system also incorporates embedded radiopaque bands that enhance fluoroscopic visualization, aiding in the precision of the procedures. The twist-lock connections secure the coaxial system together, preventing undesired movement of the components during use. The system's dimensions are: 16F ID (5.6mm) (20.2F OD, 6.8mm) x 45cm outer sheath • 14F ID (4.7mm) (16.4F OD, 5.5mm) x 53cm inner sheath • 14F OD (4.7mm OD, 1.0mm ID) x 61cm dilator • 7F ID (2.3mm) / 7F ID (2.3mm) Y-connector. Alongside the Kodiak system, Mustang balloons were used to forcefully dilate the pathway and create an initial channel into the stent lumen. The Mustang balloon's robust design facilitated forward advancement through the scar tissue, stretching it sufficiently to allow further intervention.

Stent Passage and Thrombectomy: Following the successful creation of a channel, the balloon and sheath swallow technique was utilized to advance through three overlapping sections of the stent in the ileocaval area. This technique involves sequential dilation and advancement of the sheath over the balloon, effectively dissecting through the occlusion in a controlled manner. Thrombectomy was subsequently performed using the Penumbra FLASH 16 and Excipio XL devices, which were specifically chosen for their efficacy in removing thrombus material from large vessels.

Venogram and Stent Extension: A repeat venogram was conducted post-thrombectomy, revealing competing flow into collateral channels to the right of the stent. This was indicative of significant residual stenosis and synechiae formation within the treated segment. Intravascular ultrasound (IVUS) was employed to provide a detailed view of the intraluminal and wall pathology, confirming the presence of synechiae and localized stenosis. To address this, venoplasty was performed, followed by the deployment of an Abre 12mm stent extension at the site of narrowing. This stent, known for its high radial strength and flexibility, was critical in maintaining the patency of the vessel, supporting the newly recanalized segment and preventing re-occlusion.

Outcome: The procedure was concluded with a final venogram that demonstrated restored, brisk flow through the ileocaval segment, effectively indicating successful revascularization of the previously occluded stent. The strategic use of advanced interventional devices and techniques such as the Kodiak system and Mustang balloon engulfing technique facilitated precise tissue dissection and restoration of the stent's patency. The flexibility and radial reinforcement of the introducer system were pivotal, allowing for precise and targeted

dissection of the fibrotic tissue, thus ensuring the optimal outcome of the procedure.

Conclusion:

The management of patients with complex vascular histories, such as those with recurrent DVT and complications like chronic venous insufficiency due to stent failures, demands an integrated and innovative approach. This case demonstrates the effectiveness of employing advanced interventional techniques and devices in such contexts.

These innovative techniques not only solve mechanical challenges but also contribute to long-term vessel patency and symptomatic relief, crucial for improving patient outcomes. The successful application of these techniques in this case adds valuable knowledge to the field of vascular interventional radiology, providing evidence-based strategies that can be adapted to similar clinical scenarios.

Moreover, the insights gained from such complex cases enhance our understanding of CVI management and encourage the continual advancement of interventional techniques. This progression is vital for improving care quality for patients with severe vascular diseases, ensuring they receive the most effective and personalized treatment options available. The technical feasibility and clinical success observed here advocate for broader application of these advanced interventional practices in routine clinical settings.

3. Discussion:

This case presents a complex scenario of chronic venous insufficiency (CVI) exacerbated by stent failure, illustrating the difficult and complex nature of managing such chronic vascular conditions. CVI significantly compromises quality of life, manifesting symptoms such as pain, swelling, and leg ulcers, which are particularly challenging when coupled with stent failure.(Schwein et al. 2018) This necessitates a comprehensive treatment strategy that is adaptive to the complications presented by the existing vascular hardware and the patient's unique anatomical considerations.

The employment of multiple imaging modalities plays a pivotal role in the management of CVI, particularly when stents fail. In this case, technologies like intravascular ultrasound (IVUS) and venography were indispensable. IVUS offers a detailed view of the vascular lumen and wall, providing insights into the extent of stenosis or occlusion within the stents(Shammas et al. 2019). Venography complements this by offering a functional assessment of venous flow, highlighting areas where blood flow is compromised. These imaging techniques are crucial not only for diagnosing the current state of vascular health but also for guiding the interventional strategies, ensuring that therapeutic measures are precisely targeted and effective.

Furthermore, the use of novel temporary embolic protection devices such as the Contego Excipio XL underscores the critical aspect of mitigating risk during invasive procedures. These devices are utilized for capturing and removing debris that may dislodge during interventions, thereby preventing potential complications such as pulmonary embolism.(Sangiorgi 2003) The strategic deployment of such safety measures is particularly important in patients who are already at a heightened risk due to their complex medical and surgical history and compromised pulmonary or cardiac reserve.

The case also highlights the necessity of using specialized interventional tools and techniques in synergistic fashion, such as the Kodiak Dual Port Coaxial Introducer and Mustang balloons (Boston Scientific). These tools are specifically designed to navigate and treat diseased vessels effectively, addressing issues like occlusions and heavily fibrotic segments. The Kodiak system facilitates the introduction of multiple instruments through a single access point, enhancing procedural efficiency and safety. The Mustang balloons, utilized for their ability to perform high-pressure dilation, are crucial for breaking through tough, fibrotic blockages within the stents, allowing for restoration of adequate blood flow.

The integration of these advanced techniques and technologies with expert clinical technique is essential for managing the anatomical and pathological challenges inherent in cases of severe CVI due to stent failure (Mahnken et al. 2014). Each element of the intervention—from imaging to procedural execution—must be carefully coordinated and planned out prior to procedure to ensure optimal outcomes while minimizing procedural risks and complications. This case serves as a case model of how interdisciplinary collaboration and technological innovation can successfully address some of the more challenging scenarios in vascular intervention. The application of each technique and tool not only addresses the immediate mechanical and physiological issues but also sets a precedent for future cases, potentially guiding practice and encouraging further innovation in the field of purpose-built devices to address complex venous vascular intervention.

4. Conclusion:

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1. CT Axial Imaging

Figure 1: Thrombosed Stents from Prior Reconstruction- Noted Abdominal Wall Varices

Figure 2: Complete and Partial Occlusion of Bi-Iliac Double Barrel Stent Segments

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Figure 3: Introduction of Kodiak Co-Axial System and Mustang Balloon for Expansion and Dissection Technique

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Figure 4: Gradual Balloon Dilation Performed to Stretch Chronic Thrombosis with Kodiak Advancement to Dissect Tissue and Create Intimal Lumen Channel

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Figure 5: Restoration of Patency Confirmed

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Figure 6: Successful Thrombectomy Demonstrates Residual CFV Stenosis.

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Figure 7: Venogram Demonstrates Successful Resolution of CFV Stenosis Post Segment Extension

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Figure 8: Complete Restoration of Brisk In-Line Flow Through the Stented Reconstruction, No Residual Thrombus Noted

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Figure 9: Patent Stented Segments, Complete Decompression of Abdominal Wall Varicosities

- 1. CT Axial Imaging**
- 2. Initial Venogram**
- 3. Introduction of Kodiak and Mustang Balloon for Attempted Recannulation**
- 4. Inflation and Sheath Encompassing Technique in Forward Crawl Progression**
- 5. Channel Restoration**
- 6. Thrombectomy with Penumbra Medical Flash 16 and Excipio XL for Embolic Protection**
- 7. Venoplasty and Stenting of CFV Stenosis with Medtronic Abre 12mm Venous Stent to Extend Initial Reconstruction**
- 8. Serial Venoplasty with 8mm and 16mm Balloons, Final Venography**
- 9. Follow Up-CT Axial Imaging**